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DEVELOPMENT OF GOPINATHA WORSHIP IN ODISHA (Circa. 16th - 19th Century C.E.)

Thobir Kumar Lima

Abstract:

The early history of Gopinatha is found in GopinathaCharitamrita of Vinod Chaitanya Babaji who served in the temple of Gopinatha for a long time. He has taken much trouble to collect data regarding all the traditions of Gopinatha and leaving to the readers the task of separating the kernel from the husk. It is stated that Gangavamsi king Narasimha Deva had no son to succeed him for a long time. So, he started on pilgrimage to Chitrakuta and he worshipped the image installed by Rama. The image communicated the message to him in dream as follows: "Madana Gopala is my name; I wish to go to a lovely (ramaniya) place". The king Narasimha Deva set off for his own kingdom, taking the image with him. At the time of installation, the queen gave image the name of 'Gopinatha'. The image being surrounded by the figures of Ashtasakhi (eight female associates of Krishna). The deity was installed at Remuna, as the Queen desired. Apart from the Gopinatha temple at Remuna, Balasore which is the first example of Gopinatha idol worship in Odisha, many Gopinathatemple built in different part of the Odisha through the ages. Among them, temple at Sakhigopal near Satyabadi, Temples of Gopinathapur near Jajpur, Temples of Malatira near Bhadrak and of other places are take an important role in the Growth of this cult in 13th – 14th century Odisha. But, the temples of Gopinatha cult during post-Gajapati period are not traced properly.

The growth and development of the cult of Gopinatha and the temple building activities during the post-Gajapati period is the objective of the present study. Going through the work of T.E Donaldson, R, P. Mahapatra and B.K Rath and other scholar, it is trying to locate the Gopinathacult, temples and forms of worship during 16th – 19th Century C.E.

Keywords: Temple, Gopinatha, Gajapati, cult, worship.

Introduction :

The name 'Gopinatha' is primarily a male name of Indian origin that means" *Lord of the Gopis*". This name is referred to the Hindu God Krishna. Due to the spread and influence of Srimadbhagavata and Gitagovinda among the Vaishnava religious population of Odisha, within a short period of time, instead of the Vishnu-Krishna idol or Basudeva idol, Gopinatha-Krishna idol with bifurcated human form was created. There is no doubt that idolGopinatha is the deity of Bhagavata religion. Three statues of Gopinatha are preserved in the State Museum. Said Gopinatha statues are three handed with playing flute and in the position of three folding division of the body (*Tribhanga*). In this idol, the characteristic conch and wheel of Vishnu have been left with extra geometries. This Gopinatha statue is one such deity whose worship is still seen in many places in the natural Odisha.

The first example of Gopinatha idol worship in Odisha is Kshirachora-Gopinatha in Remuna village of Balasore district. Gopinatha, founded by the Gangasemperor Narasimha Deva II (1278-1307C.E.) at Remuna Cuttack, later became known as KshirachoraGopinatha.¹ It is known from 'Madalapanji' that, the above said poet Narasimha Deva II first introduced the system of singing 'Gita Govinda' in the Sri Jagannatha temple. His reign was the period of peak development of Krishna-worship in Odisha. He was a great devoteeof Krishna. His teacher and mentor NarhariTirtha, a disciple of Madhavacharya introduced Krishna-Vishnu worship in Odisha. The construction and promotion of the Sahasa-Gopinatha-Krishna idol is a notable contribution of emperor Narasimha Deva's time. The GopinathaVigraha (having flute players carved in black granite stone in Trivangi Thani) is widely worshiped in various places in Odisha in the time of Narasimha Deva and Narahari Tirtha.

¹ B.C. Acharya, Odishare Krushna Upasana, Grantha Mandir Publication, Cuttack, 1994. pp. 149

The Archaeological investigation of KshirchoraGopinatha established that, Remuna was a temporary 'Kataka' or capital of the Ganga emperors of Odisha in the 13th-14th century AD. 'RemunaKataka' is mentioned in the copper plate inscription dated 1396 C.E. of Ganga emperor Narasingha Deva II. Remuna was a famous place in Odisha at that time. The port was shifted to Balasore from Pipili on the bank of Subarnarekha due to some reason. Even before that, the highway from the north to Cuttack-Puri was stretched through Remuna. There were many Atharvavedic Brahmin settlements in the vicinity of Remuna and this area was probably the centre of Atharvavedic Brahmin literature like Srikrushnatapini, Vrundavanatapini, which influenced the Gopinatha idol worship at Remuna. The birth place of Sridhara Swami, the famous Bhagavata speaker of India, is a village called 'Marei' located 3-4 miles north of above said Kshirachora temple. The fact that his descendants are still living here is known from the source of the historian late Parmananda Acharya.² In fact, 'Gopinatha'sKshetra' was one of the most important places of pilgrimage in Odisha at that time.

According to the text 'Chaitanya Charitamrita', the name of the deity was "*KshirchoraGopinatha*" because he stole milk for loving and supreme disciple Madhavendra Puri.³ Madhvendrapuri's memorial tomb still remains near KshirchoraGopinatha Temple. Adjacent to this memorial, the reflection of the event of 'Chaitanyacharitamrita' is described which is particularly pleasing to the audience. In it, the scene of the temple priest giving milk to Madhavendrapuri, the devotee of Gopinatha, which Gopinatha had hidden under his back of his foot, is delightfully expressed.

Sri Chaitanya's teacher Isvarapuri was a disciple of Madhavendrapuri. Madhavendrapuri was dead around 1500 AD. It is described in the said text

² P. Acharya, Studies in Orissan History, Archaeology and Archives, Archaeological Survey of India, New Delhi, 1969. pp. 422.

³ Sri Chaitanyacharitamruta, Madhyalila

that, Sri Chaitanya rested at the foot of KshirchoraGopinatha on his way to Puri. It is said that the priests of this area are hidden the idol of KshirchoraGopinatha in a pond nearby village called 'Aarmala' during the Kalapahada attack. Local worship disappeared under Muslim oppression. Around 1620-1625 A.C.E, Lord Shamananda's disciple Rasikananda Deva Goswami, during his preaching see absence of the idol in temple and discovered found that the idol of Gopinatha was submerged in water. He recovered the idol from there and re-established it in the temple. The KshirakhoraGopinatha idol that is being worshiped today is only the result of Rasikananda Dev Goswami's effort.

Growth of Gopinatha Worship in Odisha:

After the famous Gopinatha (Kshirchora) of Remuna, another Gopinatha idol was collected from somewhere in the Balasore district and is now found installed in the porch of Fakirmohan College in Balasore.⁴ Later, the location of one ancient Gopinatha idol is known in Maltira village near Bhadrak and Gopinathpur near Jajpur. The idol of Gopinatha worshiped in Dharmasala area on the banks of Brahmani river in Cuttack district is now preserved in the State Museum. The inscription on the foot of the statue says that one of an artisan or sculptor (Sutradhara) of "Avinaba Varanasi Cuttack" (Cuttack) made this statue. It is known from the Alarpur copper plate inscription of Narasimha II that, three Gopinatha statues are erected at Hirapur Village and SarkanaSasan Village near the famous Chausathi Yogini temple of Alarpur on the bank of the river Bhargavi. The said Sarkana, Baliana and Hirapur villages are adjacent to Kenduli village. In this region there is a popular rumour about the poet Jayadeva, the author of 'Gitagobinda'. Then, in Kakudia village on the banks of the Daya River, there is a magnificent Gopinatha temple built with three temples of side deity (*parsa-devata*), which is still in a dilapidated condition. Another

⁴ *ibid.*, pp. 151.

Gopinatha idol was installed in the DandamukundpurSasan near Pipili to the south of Hirapur. Gopinatha is worshiped till now near Somesvara Temple of Alguma. Then there is the Gopinatha statue of Sakthigopal and the Bengali architected style of Gopinatha statue built by the queen of Burdwan on the banks of the Markandeshwar pond in Puri are provide the other example of Gopinatha worship prevalent in Odisha. Gopinathpursasan founded near the Bhanja capital Kaladagarh by King of Ghumsara Bhaja dynasty and the Gopinatha Temple with Gopinatha idol are worshiped there. At one time it became customary to establish a Gopinatha temple on the western border of the Brahmin Sasan established by the king.

From the above details it is clear that between Remuna and Kuladagarh, there are so many Gopinatha idols worshiped and this proves that once Gopinatha idol worship was considered as a public worship in Odisha.

Except for the KshirchoraGopinatha idol, all the other Gopinatha idols appear to be similar designed. Therefore, it seems that the construction period of all these sculptures is enclosed within half a century or a century. Because of the inscription found on the statue of Gopinatha in Dharamasala only and the name 'Avinava Varanasi Kataka' is derived from it, the date of construction of the statue can be determined to be 13th century C.E. Because, during the reign of the Ganges Emperor Anangabhima (1211-1238 C.E.), 'Abhinaba Varanasi Cuttack' was established in modern Cuttack. If the date of installation of the innovative 'Varanasi Kataka' is estimated between C.E. 1220 and 1225, the date of the said DharamasalaGopinatha statue can be fixed between mid to late 13th century C.E. On the whole, it is reasonable to assume that the period of Gopinatha idol worship is 13th century C.E.

Now the following hymn is commonly practiced while worshipping the Gopinatha idols worshiped in Odisha-

“ଓଁ ଫୁଲ୍ଲେଦୀବରକାନ୍ତମିନ୍ଦୁ ବଦନଂ ବର୍ହାବତଂସ ପ୍ରିୟମ୍,
 ଶ୍ରୀବତ୍ସାଙ୍କ ମୁଦାର କୌସ୍ତୁଭଧରଂ ପୀତାମ୍ବରଂ ସୁନ୍ଦରମ୍।
 ଗୋପୀନାଂ ନୟନୋତ୍ପଳାଚ୍ଚିତ୍ତ ଚନ୍ଦ୍ର ଗୋ-ଗୋପ ସଂଘାବୃତମ୍,
 ଗୋବିନ୍ଦଂ କଳବେଶୁ ବାଦନପରଂ ଦିବ୍ୟାଙ୍ଗଭୂଷଣ ଭଜେ।”⁵

It is believed that, this hymn was created during or before the introduction of Gopinatha idol worship in the latter half of the 13th century. So there is no reason to doubt that this is an ancient meditation.⁶

Below the pedestals of the above three Gopinatha idols, eight cows on one side and eight Gopi idol on the opposite side are carved are now preserved in the State Museum, Bhubaneswar. The Gopinatha idols erected and worshiped elsewhere in Odisha are also found with two handed man like figure bearing a flute. The description of the above mentioned hymn is reflected to a considerable extent in all the above mentioned sculptures or idols and the influence Gopalila mentioned in the 10th chapter of Bhagavata on the said sculptures.

Among the Gopinatha idols found in Odisha, the Kshirchora-Gopinatha of Remuna and the Sakshigopala or Gopinatha idol of Satyabadi are famous. Gopinath idol of odisha's previous capital Cuttack was known as Sakshigopal. Forty-nine years after Sri Chaitanya's death (1533 C.E.), a devotional description about both Gopinaths is found in the Kavikarnapura's book 'Sri Chaitanya Chandodaya Natakam' (Year of Composition: 1572 C.E) as mentioned by Parmananda Sen.⁷ This proves that the worship of Kshirchora Gopinatha and Sakshigopinatha was intact in Remuna and Cuttack during and before Sri Chaitanya's time.

⁵ ibid., pp. 150.

⁶ This hymn was originally written and used by Sri Sankaracharya and derived from the text of Sanatana Goswami.

⁷ Kabikarnapura, Sri Caitanya Chandrodaya Natakam, pp. 186-189.

In Odisha, the popularization of the Bhagavata Purana led to the vogue of Gopinatha idols from the 13th century onwards, but in the neighbouring province of Bangal, even after Sri Chaitanya's death, only four-handed Vishnu idols were prevalent. Reliable proof of about it comes from the play written by Kavi Karnapur. In this play, the antiquity of Sakshigopal's idol of Cuttack and other Gopinatha idols worshiped and established in many other places in Odisha is recognised as well as the proponents of worshipping only the idols of four-handed Vishnu are declared to be 'deluded'.⁸ It is believed that the worship of the two handed Gopinatha idol started in Odisha first. In the neighbouring Bangal and Bihar, Radha-Krishna idol worship in the pre-Chaitanya period is rare, not even a single Krishna idol is found. Historian Rakhhal Das Banerjee has given a clear opinion in this regard.⁹

Thus, among the deities worshiped in Odisha, Sakshigopinatha or Gopala also experienced many changes in fortunes. The above text 'Chaitanyacharitamrita' states that at the time of Sri Chaitanya's arrival at Puri (1509-10 C.E.). Sakshigopinatha was being worshiped at Cuttack. According to the story of *Badabipra* and *Sanabipra* Gopinatha idol escaped from Vrindavana to Kanchi on his own. From there, the SuryavamsiGajapati king of Odisha Purusottama Dev (1467-1497 C.E.) brought the idol to Cuttack and arranged his service and worship. Even though there are many evidences of Gopinatha idol worship in Odisha long before the reign of Purusottamadeva, also the legend has created for the book 'Chaitanya-charitamrita'. The structure of the Sakshi Gopinatha statue is similar to other Gopinatha idols of Odisha. It is not like the North Indian Vrundavana sculpture or the South Indian Kanchi sculpture. In relation to KshirchoraGopinatha and Sakshigopinatha, the text of 'Chaitanya-

⁸ ibid. 187-188

⁹ New Imperial Series, Vol. XLVII, (1933), P. 127- "Not only do we find a very great scarcity of combined images of Krishna and Radha in the eastern school, but no image of Krishna by Himself earlier than the fifteenth century has been discovered anywhere in Bengal and Bihar. The popularity of Radha Krishna cult, in the north-eastern provinces of India appears to-date from the advent of the great reformer Sri Chaitanya.

charitamrita' is most important source which is necessary to recognise both legends and for their historical discussion.

The Sakshigopinatha image once established in Cuttack, became established in Satyavadi over the time, is also very interesting in the page of history. A stone inscription in the Puri Jagannatha temple of SuryavamsiGajapatiPurusottam Deva states that the name of the place where the Gopala idol was worshiped in Cuttack was 'GopalapriyaJagati'.¹⁰ In 1568 C.E., before Kalapahad captured Cuttack and destroyed the Gopala Temple, some learned person secretly moved the Sri Gopala idol from Cuttack. Later, Ramachandra Deva (1568-1600 C.E), the first king of the Bhoi dynasty established his capital at Khurda and installed a new temple for Sri Gopala in Khurda. Later, due to the Muslim oppression of Khurdagarh, a king of Khurda installed the idol in a new temple at RathpurGarh near Jatani. After that Mughal Subedar Takikhan raided the Rathipur temple, the Sakshigopal's idol was shifted to Kantalabai village near Bhushandpur station on the bank of Chilika, where a temple was built for him and enshrined in it. Finally, during the Marahatta dynasty, Ramachandra Deva, king of Puri, transferred the idol from Kantalbai to Satyavadi. A new temple was built for Sakshigopala in Satyavadi and the idol of Sri Sakshigopala is worshiped in this temple till date. Being situated on the highway leading to Satavadi-Puri, the shrine of Sakshigopinatha is especially popular among pilgrims of Puri.

The advent of Sridhara Swami in the 14th century and the composition of the famous 'Bhagavata Purana', made the Bhagavat-narrative Srikrishna's love theme in Gopa gain popular among the Odisha's people. It is known from a stone carving preserved in the State Museum.

On the bank of the Yamuna is a Kadamba tree, with three carved Gopi statues on both sides of the tree. Between the branches of the Kadamba tree,

¹⁰ The statement is proved from the line “ବାରାଣସୀ କଟକେ ଶ୍ରୀନଥରେ ଗୋପାଳପ୍ରିୟ ଜଗତୀର ଦକ୍ଷିଣ ମେଢ଼ରେ ବଡ଼ ଅବକାଶେ”

Lord Krishna himself is revealed as self-concealed. The gopi-periphery bifurcations are suspended in the tree branches. The expressions of the gopis are beautifully reflected in their expressions of anguish and pleading with Lord Krishna. The depiction of the Yamuna water body with fish-scorpion-crooks touching the feet of the gopis is vivid in the art of carving. In Odisha of the 14th century, the spread of Bhaktiism expressed at the base of the 'Basahran' music described in the Bhagavat Purana can be inferred from the said landscape.

The wave and trend of Krishna-bhakti is seen to have gradually declined by the latter half of the fifteenth century. Gajapati Puruchottam Deva (1467-1497 AD) was the 'beloved of Gopala' as mentioned earlier. It is probably during his reign that the beautiful 'Balagopala' idols from the pre-existing Gopinatha idols were made and established as idols in Odisha. It was the great attraction of the boy Srikrishna's Gopalila, which is described in the Bhagavata Purana, which was very active. One such 'Balagopala' sculpture is kept in the State Museum. The 'Balagopala' sculpture that playing the flute is made on Blackstone. The beautiful display of the clothes worn on the waist and the ornaments adorned around the neck are skilfully carving in the said vigraha.

The emergence and propagation of prominent Vaishnavism groups including Sri Chaitanya and Panchasakha, the trend of Krishna-worship seems to have spread to different regions of Odisha in the 16th century. We get its example from Srigopalajiu temple established in Sambalpur city. Bansigopala, the brother of Madangopala Singh Dev, the first Chauhan king of Sonapur, took initiation of Monk and established Srigopaljiu monastery (*Mathas*) and temple in Sambalpur¹¹ Sonapur was originally a zamindari of the Patna state and was considered a tributary

¹¹ Nilamani Senapati and N.K. Sahu, *Orissa District Gazetteers: Balangir*, Orissa Government Press, Cuttack, 1968. Pp. 475.

state of Sambalpur in the mid-16th century. Therefore, it may be correct the above-mentioned Bansigopala, brother of Sonepur king established the Gopalajiu temple in Sambalpur.

A Gopala temple was built near the *Papakshaya Ghat* on the Mahanadi, two miles south of Binika within the district of modern Balangir during the above discussed period. Legend says that Anangbhimadeva, the king of the Ganges, absolved the sin here. Anangbhimadeva (1211-1238 C.E.) defeated the Kalachuri kingdom from the Sambalpur-Sonpur region and annexed it to his kingdom. After winning the battle with the Kalachuris, Anangbhimadeva took a holy bath at this place in the river and since then this place in the river is called '*Papatsaya Ghat*' or '*Papabinashini Ghat*'. Anangbhimadeva erected the Kapilaswara Shiva temple at Chauda, two miles away from this place, as a memorial of the said holy bath. Said Gopal temple was probably built near this Papakshaya ghat of Mahanadi. Because, it is said that, there is no connection of '*Papakshaya ghat*' with the said Gopala temple. People still consider it a meritorious act to see Kapilaswar Shiva in Charda after taking a bath at Papakshaya Ghat during Solar eclipse or lunar eclipse (Suryaparaga o Chandragrahana). Therefore, it is assumed that the historic Papakshaya Ghat of the said Gopal Mandir was probably built during the peak development period of Krishna-worship in 16th century.

Due to the spread of Krishna-worship, Gopaljiu Temple, Brundadavanbihari temple, and Gopinatha temple appear to have been built at Sonepur. These temples were probably built in the 15th century during the reign of the Chauhan dynasty, because the idol of Sri Radha is not found on the left side of Gopinatha. Therefore, it is possible that the said temple and idol were established before the advent of Radha-worship with Krishna. In this context, the famous and revered Gopinath idol is also worth mentioning. Devagarh, the capital of Bamanda State, is located within Sambalpur. The construction period of this Gopinatha temple is not earlier than 16th century. Krishna idol in Brahampura temple built during the

aforesaid period in Sambalpur city deserves special mention in this context. On one side of the door of this temple, there is a carved image of Srikrishna seated on a lotus in *Trivanga (three division of the body)* position. On the other side of the door, nine incarnations-Vishnu idol is erected. Perhaps the main intention of the builder was to depict Lord Krishna as Supreme Lord and to depict lord Krishana as the father of all incarnations carved on the other side of the door. The influence of Bhagavat Purana is clear.

A small temple of Krishna is erected to the west of Satyanarayana temple in the middle of the Puri temple. The temple faces north and statue of Krishna erected here. To the west of the Krishna temple is a Radhakrishna temple facing north at the base of the eastern banyan tree. Here the Krishna idol is also made of stone, but Radha idol is made on eight metals. There is no doubt that the statue of Radha was installed near Krishna idol at a later date.

It is known from history that another Shrikrishna idol installed inside the Puri temple was broken into pieces in 1568 C.E. After the death of Gajapati Mukund Deva, due to the lack of proper resistance, the attack on the Jagannath Temple by Kalapahad, the commander of Bengal Sultan was very intense, terrifying and destructive. Therefore, its heart-wrenching memory has remained etched in the psyche of the Odishan people till now. The story of the attack described in Madalapanji is also supported by contemporary Muslim chronicles. It is said that king of Bengal Suleman Karrani demolished the Jagannatha temple and on his orders the idol of Lord Krishna was broken into pieces and thrown into the canal. Although there is no specific description about the shape of the Shrikrishna idol in Puri temple, it is assumed to be similar to other contemporary Gopinatha or Shrikrishna idols of Odisha.

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